

SYNTHESIS OF SUBSTITUTED AMINOPHENOXAZINES

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Several aminophenoxazines containing alkyl and/or halogen groupings have been prepared.

In continuation of the work carried out in this laboratory (Sen and Sharma, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 671; 1957, 34, 877) several aminophenoxazines containing different substituents have been prepared with a view to studying the effect of these substituents on the tuberculostatic activity (Boothroyd *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1504).

The aminophenoxazines were prepared by the catalytic reduction of the nitrophenoxazine using Adams' catalyst and acetic acid. The bases were isolated in their oxidised form as imine hydrochloride. As the hydrochlorides did not show satisfactory melting points due to the presence of some water-insoluble impurities, the bases were characterised through their picrates. Two of the hydrochlorides were isolated from the picrates by treating them with 40% NaOH solution, extracting with benzene, drying, and then passing dry HCl gas through it.

The nitrophenoxazines were prepared by refluxing the corresponding diphenylamines with ethanolic NaOH (2*N*).

The required diphenylamines were prepared by the condensation of *o*-aminophenol, 4-methyl-2-aminophenol and 4-chloro-2-aminophenol with appropriate dinitrohalogenobenzenes having a reactive chlorine atom.

EXPERIMENTAL

2'-Hydroxy-2:4-dinitro-5-methyl-6-iododiphenylamine (I).—To a suspension of 1-chloro-2-iodo-3-methyl-4:6-dinitrobenzene (3 g.) and *o*-aminophenol (1.4 g.) in ethanol (20 c.c.) sodium acetate solution (10 c.c., ca. 2 *N*) was added under stirring. The mixture was refluxed for 2 hours over a steam bath. After cooling, the diphenylamine was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol in shining small crystals, m.p. 122°, yield 3.5g. (Found: N, 10.43. $C_{13}H_{10}O_2N_2I$ requires N, 10.12%). In a similar way the following diphenylamines were prepared (Table I).

TABLE I

Amines.	M.P.	Yield	% Nitrogen	
			Found.	Calc.
<i>2'-Hydroxy-5'-methyl-2:4-dinitro-5-methyl-6-iodo-D</i> *	110°	67%	10.05	9.79
<i>2'-Hydroxy-5'-chloro-2:4-dinitro-5-methyl-6-iodo-D</i>	68°	85	9.47	9.34
<i>2'-Hydroxy-5'-chloro-2:4-dinitro-5-ethyl-D</i>	195°	72	12.73	12.48
<i>(2'-Hydroxy-5'-chlorophenyl)-2:4-dinitro-1-N</i> ^a	210°	81	13.13	12.84
<i>(2'-Hydroxy-5'-chlorophenyl)-2:4-dinitro-1-N</i>	190°	92	12.25	12.08
<i>(2'-Hydroxyphenyl)-1:6-dinitro-2-N</i>	155°	77	13.64	13.41
<i>(2'-Hydroxy-5'-methylphenyl)-1:6-dinitro-2-N</i>	166°	89	12.99	12.84

* D and N denote respectively diphenylamine and naphthylamine.

1-Iodo-2-methyl-3-nitrophenoxazine.—2'-Hydroxy-2:4-dinitro-5-methyl-6-iododiphenylamine (3g.) was suspended in ethanol (15 c.c.) and 2*N*-NaOH (~ 10 c.c.) was added under stirring. Colour of the reaction mixture instantaneously darkened on the addition of the alkali solution, after which the mixture was refluxed for half an hour on a steam bath. On cooling in a freezing mixture, a dark reddish brown solid separated out. It was filtered, washed with NaOH solution (dil.) followed by a little ethanol, and recrystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 205°, yield 2g. (Found: N, 7.97. $C_{13}H_9O_3N_2I$ requires N, 7.60%). The other nitrophenoxazines were prepared in a similar way (Table II).

TABLE II

Phenoxazine.	M.P.	Yield.	% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.
1-Iodo-2:7-dimethyl-3-nitro-	285°	81.0%	7.51	7.33
1-Iodo-2-methyl-7 chloro-3-nitro-	225°	79.6	7.27	6.95
2-Ethyl-7 chloro-3-nitro-	220°	85.6	9.82	9.63
2-Nitro -6 methyl-3:4 benzo-	> 300°	92.0	10.28	10.00
2-Nitro -6 chloro-3:4 benzo-	> 300°	97.0	9.54	9.31
1:2-(3'-Nitrobenzo)-	> 300°	87.2	10.67	10.52
1:2-(3'-Nitrobenzo)-6-methyl-	262°	76.0	10.41	10.00

Aminophenoxazines.—The nitrophenoxazine (1g.) was suspended in glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.) and reduced in an atmosphere of hydrogen (60 lb. pressure) for 4 hours using Adams' catalyst (50 mg.). A light green or brown coloured solution was obtained on reduction, which darkened on exposure to air. The reduced solution was quickly filtered and concentrated in vacuum to approximately 10 c.c. On neutralising the solution with ammonium hydroxide, the base separated out.

The base was dissolved in benzene and converted into the hydrochloride by passing dry HCl gas through the dry benzene solution. On addition of a saturated picric acid solution to the filtered aqueous solution of the imine hydrochloride, the picrate separated out as a green or greenish yellow precipitate, which was washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol.

The melting points and the analyses of the picrates obtained from the iminophenoxazines are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Phenoxazine.	M.P.	% Nitrogen.	
		Found.	Calc.
3-Amino-1-iodo -2 methyl-	102°	12.58	12.39
3-Amino-1-iodo-2:7-dimethyl-	131°	12.31	12.09
3-Amino-1-iodo-2-methyl-7-chloro-	137°	11.93	11.77
3-Amino-2-ethyl-7-chloro-	197°	14.62	14.35
2-Amino-6-methyl-3:4-benzo-	167°	14.87	14.67
2-Amino-6-chloro-3:4-benzo-	216°	14.13	14.07
1:2-(3'-Aminobenzo)-	109°	15.36	15.11
1:2-(3'-Aminobenzo)-6-methyl-	147°	14.79	14.67

3-Amino-2-ethyl-7-chlorophenoxazine Hydrochloride.—The picrate of 3-amino-2-ethyl-7-chlorophenoxazine (0.5 g.) was treated with 40% NaOH solution (5 c.c.) and stirred for 15 minutes. It was extracted with benzene; the benzene extract was dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate, and dry HCl gas was passed through it in the cold till saturation. It was then filtered and the solid obtained was crystallised from absolute ethanol, m.p. 263° (decomp.). (Found: N, 9.29. $C_{14}H_{14}ON_2Cl_2$ requires N, 9.42%).

1:2-(3'-Aminobenzo)-6-methylphenoxazine hydrochloride was prepared exactly in the same way as above using the picrate of 1:2-(3'-aminobenzo)-6-methylphenoxazine; m.p. 287° (decomp.). (Found: N, 9.13. $C_{17}H_{18}ON_2Cl$ requires N, 9.41%).

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Received March 21, 1960.